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Review Article

SIDEROBLASTIC ANEMIA DIAGNOSIS AND MANAGEMENT

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Abstract:

Introduction: Sideroblastic anemia (SA), when defined 5 decades ago, was already recognized to occur in heterogeneous settings, including as familial or acquired disease. Since then, the perspective of SA has become considerably widened with respect to distinct clinical phenotypes and discrete causes as well. Presence of telltale ring sideroblasts in the bone marrow aspirate smear is the unique feature that is required for initial diagnosis and typifies the forms of SA.

Aim of work: This review discusses the most recent approach to sideroblastic anemia.

Methodology: We run a systematic search for Sideroblastic Anemia using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). Relevant studies were retrieved and screened. Only full articles were included.

Conclusions: Despite the fact that SA is uncommon, it has to be considered in all patients with unexplained anemia of any severity. Detailed medical history, clinical examination, and basic laboratory data are corner stone to approach this disease. Suggestive clinical features includes a history of chronic anemia, family history of anemia, presence of neurologic abnormalities, myopathy, lactic acidosis. The principal treatments is directed towards correction of the identified reversible cause. Cases of XLSA with microcytic anemia, are effectively corrected with thiamin supplements. Other modalities of treatment comprise red cell transfusion for severe anemia, excess iron removal. Phlebotomy is recommended for mild anemia, while iron chelation is reserved for patients with severe/transfusion dependent anemia.

Key words: Sideroblastic Anemia, diagnosis, Management

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INTRODUCTION:

Sideroblastic anemia (SA), when defined 5 decades ago, was already recognized to occur in heterogeneous settings, including as familial or acquired disease [1]. Since then, the perspective of SA has become considerably widened with respect to distinct clinical phenotypes and discrete causes as well [2]. Presence of telltale ring sideroblasts in the bone marrow aspirate smear is the unique feature that is required for initial diagnosis and typifies the forms of SA.

In such occasion, erythroblasts contain characteristic numerous coarse Prussian blue-positive granules, distributed in a perinuclear manner. Such granules represent a pathologic accumulation of iron in within the mitochondria.

Composing iron and protoporphyrin IX, heme synthesis is enhanced in the mitochondrion by ferrochelatase (FECH). The quantity of iron used by an erythron to produce hemoglobin is well appreciated. Nearly about 80% of the body heme assorted as part of hemoglobin. Also, more than two-thirds of the body irons are used in heme production. Furthermore, iron imported into mitochondria is also used to generate iron-sulfur (Fe-S) clusters, which in turn act as essential prosthetic groups in certain proteins. These proteins regulate the cellular uptake and storage of iron, heme synthesis, iron regulatory protein 1 (IRP1), and FECH itself [3].

The general concepts related to the pathogenesis of the SAs have emerged from discoveries of the genetic defects underlying various congenital SAs (CSAs). Based on our current knowledge, the distinct pathology is primarily linked to abnormalities in the pathways of heme biosynthesis and Fe-S biogenesis pathways in addition to defects in the translation of mitochondrial encoded proteins. Nevertheless, the certain consequence events that lead to a ring sideroblast formation and anemia is intensely not understood.

Importantly, in the common SAs circumstances, the body iron metabolism is also highly altered. So that, the associated ineffective erythropoiesis elicits a systemic iron overload state, which in turn affects clinical features as well as prognosis, as will come after.

This review discusses the most recent approach to sideroblastic anemia.

METHODOLOGY:

We run a systematic search for Sideroblastic Anemia

using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). Relevant studies were retrieved and screened. Only full articles were included.

The key words used in the search were: Sideroblastic Anemia, diagnosis, Management

DIAGNOSIS

The SAs can be classified into CSA and acquired forms. The CSAs, the inherited type, may not present at birth, and sometimes may not be recognized until adulthood.

Because of certain distinctive treatments and considerably different prognoses, it is highly essential to distinguish the later-onset CSA from the acquired SA. As summarized later, reaching a specific diagnosis basically relies on type of the anemia (eg, microcytic, normocytic, or macrocytic), age of clinical onset, associated syndromic features, and molecular genetic diagnostics.

Nonsyndromic CSAs

X-linked SA is the most common type of CSA, constituting about 40% of cases.⁽⁴⁾ It is often mild or asymptomatic. It may be discovered only in young adulthood or later life. Occasionally, severe cases could also present in infancy or childhood. Rarely, it might be associated with an in utero (often lethal) phenotype.⁴ It is uncommon to be seen in women as a result of acquired inactivation of skewed X chromosome in hematopoietic tissue, which occurs within among the advanced age group and ,exceptionally, among females during childhood.

Mutations in ALAS2, the first and rate-limiting enzyme of heme synthesis, lead to XLSA. Yet, more than 80 distinct mutations have been identified in more than 120 unrelated kindreds.⁵ About one-fifth of the mutations have occurred in more than one family, and nearly one-third of probands are female. Most of these mutations are missense alleles.

The autosomal recessive CSA is caused by mutations in SLC25A38, accounting for about 15% of cases. Of all patients with CSA, 4% of the cases present at birth or in early childhood as a severe transfusion-dependent microcytic hypochromic anemia. The genetic circumstances behind this type involve a defect in the erythroid-specific mitochondrial inner membrane, particularly, the carrier protein SLC25A38. This protein is an amino acid transporter required for importing the glycine into mitochondria

and exchanging glycine for ALA during the primary steps of heme synthesis [6]. Among 31 patients so far reported, mutations detected were found to be heterogeneous. Also, they include missense, nonsense, and splicing errors. Indeed, one-fourth of these mutations are recurrent in unrelated families [7]. Because of its autosomal pattern, this type of anemia is more likely to be seen in children of consanguineous parentage.

A single case of a microcytic hypochromic transfusion-dependent SA presenting in midlife has been attributed to a homozygous splice site mutation in the glutaredoxin 5 (GLRX5) gene [8].

Erythropoietic protoporphyria (EPP) is a disorder featured by marked deficiency of FECH.16 Mild anemia was observed in most patients [9]. Interestingly, ring sideroblasts have been documented in only 10 patients.

The clinical laboratory finding for the nonsyndromic CSAs is erythrocyte microcytosis and hypochromia along with an elevated red cell distribution width (RDW). It is mandatory to exclude other causes of microcytic anemia including iron deficiency and thalassemia. One important exception to the previous clue is that most females expressing XLSA tend to have a normal or increased MCV. In severely affected females, erythroid cells with a nonfunctional ALAS2 enzyme presumably do not develop into viable erythrocytes, so that the patients' circulating red cells represent progeny of the residual normal clone released from marrow at an accelerated rate in response to the anemia. In contrast, some females with milder anemia exhibit a biphasic red cell volume that is characterized by forms of normocytic and microcytic cells. Nonanemic female carrying this trait could also exhibit a small microcytic erythrocyte forms, but when present, may indicate the correct diagnosis in a related male proband. Nonetheless, the morphologic features of the anemia in caused by SLC25A38 mutations are indistinguishable from males with XLSA.

However, it is an exception for XLSA to present in early childhood. Therefore, mutations in SLC25A38 have been excluded in all individuals presenting with microcytic CSA, either during infancy or early childhood. As with all subtypes of CSAs, the certain diagnosis relies on having a genetic defect shown by mutation analysis.

Syndromic CSAs

XLSA with ataxia (XLSA/A) is described in 4

kindreds, so far, due to mutations in the mitochondrial adenosine triphosphate-binding cassette transporter ABCB7. This transporter exports Fe-S clusters generated in mitochondria to be used in synthesis of proteins [10]. It is suggested that ABCB7 malfunction disturbs iron metabolism at cellular and mitochondrial levels due to its effects on IRP1.

Distinguishing the syndromic CSAs from the nonsyndromic CSAs depends on the presence of nonhematologic manifestations. However, clinical features may be vague or not yet fully manifest at the time of presentation and, therefore, makes recognition on clinical basis too shady. Presented by mild to moderate microcytic SA, XLSA/A is accompanied by neurologic symptoms, including delayed motor and cognitive development, incoordination, and cerebellar hypoplasia. Nevertheless, female carriers of XLSA/A don't present with neurologic manifestations, apart from mild hematologic abnormalities such as an increased RDW and siderocytes in peripheral blood smear.

The syndrome of CSA, autosomal recessive, is also associated with central nervous system (CNS) abnormalities, cardiomyopathy, and sensorineural hearing loss [11]. Presenting scenarios include B-cell immunodeficiency, periodic fevers, and developmental delay (SIFD) presents in infancy. Importantly, the observed severe microcytic anemia usually requires chronic transfusion or stem cell transplantation.

The Pearson marrow-pancreas syndrome usually presents during the first 6 months of life. Presenting symptoms include anemia, metabolic acidosis, failure to thrive, and exocrine pancreatic insufficiency. Indeed, hepatic and renal failure are observed. It is important to highlight that this syndrome might be missed initially due to absence of the metabolic derangements. It may be mistaken for Diamond-Blackfan anemia specially when ring sideroblasts are infrequent or in cases of marked erythroid hypoplasia.¹² The anemia tends to be severe and is most often macrocytic. Bone marrow examination shows a remarkable vacuolization of erythroid and myeloid progenitors.

Mitochondrial abnormalities in skeletal muscles most characterized by dense inclusions that appear as linear arrays of cristae. Despite the fact that one or several encoded transfer RNAs (tRNA) are deleted approximately in all cases, there is no a common deleted region in all patients. This, in turn, is expected to lead to a generalized defect in translation

of mitochondrial protein. However, and like many other forms of CSA, there is lack of comprehensive explanation for mechanism of mitochondrial iron accumulation. Diagnostic clues include deletions (most often of 4977 bp), rearrangements, or mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) duplications [13]. It is important to highlight that there is high variability of affected tissues due to the mtDNA heteroplasmy at cellular and organ levels.

MLASA which denotes for myopathy, lactic acidosis, and SA, is an autosomal recessive disorder that may be encountered during infancy, childhood, or adolescence. The picture of bone marrow examination, vacuolization, is almost identical to that of Pearson marrow-pancreas syndrome. Collectively, clinical findings includes weakness of skeletal muscles, lactic acidosis, and severe normocytic anemia.

Thiamine-responsive megaloblastic anemia (TRMA) syndrome is caused by nonsense or frameshift mutations that result in complete loss-of-function alleles [14]. Typically manifests during infancy and adolescence as a triad of megaloblastic anemia, sensorineural deafness, and non-type I diabetes mellitus. In such instance, macrocytic anemia is associated with megaloblastic changes, variable neutropenia, and thrombocytopenia. Classically known, macrocytic megaloblastic anemia arises from defective synthesis of nucleic acid which could be attributed to thiamine or folate deficiency [15].

Undefined CSAs

Approximately, 40% of CSA cases are molecularly unexplained. In such instances, autosomal recessive as well as X-linked defects are possible. They could be shown in previously identified genes.

Alternatively, novel insights of genes involved in heme, Fe-S cluster production, and mitochondrial proteins related to iron processing are yet to be identified.

Acquired Clonal SAs

This type is the most common SA encountered in clinical practice. Acquired Clonal SA pattern is insidious. Middle and old ages are the most affected groups. The vast majority of cases are discovered during a routine examination or in association with different complains. The anemia is moderately severe and exhibits biphasic fashion, normocytic or macrocytic due to the presence of a hypochromic erythrocyte on the blood smear.(36)

As released by World Health Organization

classification of hematopoietic neoplasms, three categories are distinguished. Refractory anemia with ring sideroblasts (RARS), RARS with thrombocytosis (RARS-T), and refractory cytopenia with multilineage dysplasia and ring sideroblasts (RCMD-RS).(37) As is discussed later, these disorders are featured on a continuous phenotypic spectrum that is chiefly related to somatic mutations in a certain class of genes. Thereafter, secondary mutations of such genes supervene to modify the morphologic and clinical phenotypes.

During the early studies focusing on heme biosynthesis, no dependable defects in protoporphyrin synthesis in marrow cells were identified. Only, one single case was found to have somatic ALAS2 mutation.¹⁶ However, about one-half of patients were revealed to have a mild to moderate increase of erythrocyte protoporphyrin, along with defective marrow FECH activity. Rarely, clinical or biochemical features resemble EPP. It suggested to be caused by an acquired deletion of the FECH allele.¹⁷

DISEASE COURSES AND TREATMENT OPTIONS

Clinical courses of SA are highly dependent on the underlying cause as well as on the supportive care provided, particularly in the severe cases.

Nonsyndromic CSA

In patients with X-linked SA, the anemia is usually mild to moderate in severity and remains so at the set point determined by the extent of ALAS2 enzyme impairment. Approximately, two-thirds of cases, the anemia corrected by pyridoxine supplements which enhances functions of some ALAS2 mutants. On average, the hemoglobin level normalizes in about one-third of responders. On the other hand, severe anemia that failed to respond by pyridoxine dictates transfusion dependence and collateral iron overload. Patients with SLC25A38 defects usually presents with uniformly severe anemia that requires regular lifelong transfusions. Hematopoietic stem cell transplantation has been successful in 5 unreported cases. In one patient with, transfusions resulted in a worse deterioration which, then, was slightly reversed with iron chelation using deferoxamine.

Anemia associated with EPP is often mild and requires no treatment. On the contrary, these patients tend to have lifelong course of photosensitivity and complications may arise suddenly. Progressive liver disease has been observed in 2% of cases which, thereafter, required liver and/or bone marrow transplantation [18].

Syndromic CSA

During the clinical course in the XLSA/A syndrome, non-hematologic features of neurologic changes often prevail and the outcome counts on supportive and rehabilitative services.

Due to the severity and progressive pattern of SIFD, 53% of cases early died from cardiac or multiorgan failure. Supportive treatment has included regular transfusions and immunoglobulin infusions in most patients. Hematopoietic stem cell transplantation was successful in one, correcting the anemia and immunodeficiency.

Clinical course in patients with the MLASA syndromes is unpredictable. Symptoms at presentation are highly variable even within the same family.¹⁹ . Importantly, spontaneous improvement was observed among some patients with YARS2 defects. Two cases with severe disease, died at ages 3 months and 18 years as result of cardiomyopathy. However, many patients have survived into adulthood.

In TRMA syndrome, cases are treated with thiamine (vitamin B1) in pharmacologic doses. It was observed to corrects the anemia and the diabetes to a good extent. Nevertheless, it has been found ineffective in adulthood.

Acquired Clonal SA

RARS and RARS-T variants have a stable nonprogressive pattern of anemia. A blood transfusion is obligate for symptomatic anemia, particularly, at advanced age or in the presence of other comorbidities. Patients with RCMD-RS tend to have more severe anemia. In addition, their survival rate is decreased and 5% of cases transform into acute leukemia [20].

For myelodysplastic syndromes with ring sideroblast variants, trials have been using erythropoietin with or without GCSF and various drugs (eg, 5-azacytidine and decitabine, etanercept, antithymocyte globulin, thalidomide, and valproic acid).

limited to only 50%. Splenectomy operation has often been considered. It was sporadically performed in patients with CSA, presented with severe anemia and huge splenomegaly. On the other hand, this operation is invariably complicated by postoperative thromboembolic events and fatal outcomes. Therefore, this procedure is advised to be contraindicated [21].

CONCLUSIONS:

Despite the fact that SA is uncommon, it has to be considered in all patients with unexplained anemia of any severity. Detailed medical history, clinical examination, and basic laboratory data are corner stone to approach this disease. Suggestive clinical features includes a history of chronic anemia, family history of anemia, presence of neurologic abnormalities, myopathy, lactic acidosis.

On the bone marrow aspirate smear, If the pathognomonic ring sideroblasts are evident, a careful review of the patient's variety of clinical findings aids in narrowing the differential diagnosis. The erythrocyte indices and morphology are also of significant help. Accurate erythrocyte morphology is best obtained before any transfusion, which in turn can mask the abnormalities (eg, a microcytosis and hypochromia).

When the causative gene is identified, a definitive diagnosis of a CSA is reached by mutation analysis. In cases of CSA, a search for affected family members is recommended. Evaluation and monitoring for iron overload are indicated by biochemical testing (serum transferrin saturation and ferritin), as well as, assessment of organ involvement via magnetic resonance imaging.

The principal treatment is directed towards correction of the identified reversible cause. Cases of XLSA with microcytic anemia are effectively corrected with thiamin supplements. Other modalities of treatment comprise red cell transfusion for severe anemia, excess iron removal. Phlebotomy is recommended for mild anemia, while iron chelation is reserved for patients with severe/transfusion dependent anemia.

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